

A Wizard for Kids: A Platform for Improvised Child–Robot Interactions

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Figure 1: Our Wizard-of-Oz interface enables easy prototyping and testing of Human-Robot Interactions in highly unpredictable settings.

Abstract

We present an interface designed to operate social robots in a highly unpredictable context: a classroom, supporting user-centered design of innovative child–robot interactions. Having a functional prototype enables rich user data elicitation and analysis, essential for understanding user needs and deriving meaningful requirements. Deploying robots outside controlled laboratory conditions into a classroom, however, introduces challenges related to safety, robustness, and managing multiple, often noisy, interactions. Our system addresses these challenges by providing a safe, flexible and resilient interface that ensures safe operation while allowing improvisation and adaptability to unpredictable children’s behaviors. The interface aims to be intuitive for non-expert users and support everyday teaching and learning activities in the classrooms. By prioritizing usability, modularity, and robustness, our approach facilitates iterative design, accelerates the transition from Wizard-of-Oz prototyping to autonomous behaviors, and contributes to

making child–robot interaction technologies more accessible and practical for diverse application domains.

CCS Concepts

• **Human-centered computing** → **User interface design**; *User centered design*; Empirical studies in interaction design; • **Computer systems organization** → **External interfaces for robotics**.

Keywords

Wizard-of-Oz, Human–Robot Interaction, Social Robots, User Interface Design

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1 Introduction

In Human-Robot Interaction (HRI) research, the Wizard-of-Oz (WoZ) paradigm [14] serves as a fundamental method for testing, prototyping, and conducting experimental analyses. A human operator, referred to as the “wizard”, secretly sends commands to the robot,

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which interacts with users who are unaware of the operator’s involvement. In specific contexts, like Child-Robot Interaction (CRI), the WoZ often represents the only viable approach to adapt to the unpredictability of children’s behavior [16] and operate effectively in noisy, crowded environments like schools (particularly challenging for robot perception and control algorithms). In other HRI scenarios, advanced WoZ interfaces are essential for testing interaction paradigms and guiding the transition to real autonomy, helping to address the ethical issues concerning user deception [14, 18]. The ideal WoZ system should support *improvisation*, that is it should be capable of handling highly unpredictable behaviors (e.g. children engaged in collaborative tasks), unstructured settings (such as noisy and crowded schools) and novel situations, as often encountered in HRI during early stages of interactive design such as those required for running usage research [7]. Instrumental for the understanding of users’ needs, usage research entails different techniques for gathering and analyzing user data from which user requirements can be derived. In order to support it, the WoZ should provide a great degree of flexibility to accommodate for early introduction in the context of use and adapt to yet to be studied users’ behaviours. Ideally, a WoZ system should feature a modular interface that can adapt to different contexts and user profiles, support the integration of robot autonomy, and be transferable across different robotic platforms. Furthermore, it is desirable to provide easy-to-use interfaces that enable even inexperienced operators to control robots that interact with people, accounting for the different work roles inherent to the specific context. Finally, the interface should also incorporate elements of robot’s perception (e.g., to infer the willingness of users to interact [1, 4]) and actuation (e.g., the ability to generate proactive behaviors [5, 17]), to support the development of full robot autonomy or assist remote teleoperation by lay operators.

We propose a WoZ system that emphasizes ease of use, adaptability, and scalability, with a focus on supporting improvisation. The system is fully integrated with Robot Operating System 2 (ROS2), enabling easy deployment in the HRI community. Recently proposed WoZ platforms differ significantly in their purpose, target users, and required expertise. *HRISudio* [12] is a comprehensive, researcher-oriented environment that supports experiment design, protocol standardization, data management, and reproducibility. While well suited for creating and analyzing structured studies, it is not designed for rapid, improvisational control or child-facing deployments. *OpenWoZ* [8] supports runtime reconfiguration and multi-operator control, but it requires substantial programming expertise to extend, and it is not readily deployable by non-expert users. *Polonius* [10] provides powerful real-time logging and scripting capabilities, but it is built on ROS1 and depends on predefined scripts, limiting flexibility in dynamic scenarios. *WoZ4U* [15] provides a configurable web-based WoZ interface for Pepper, with interaction elements defined upfront via configuration files and limited guidance on cross-robot portability. In contrast to these cited works, our system is Open Access and lightweight, and focuses on live, high-responsiveness WoZ control in classroom settings with children. It requires no programming knowledge to operate during experiments, uses minimal robot-specific code (a small ROS2 adapter), emphasizes safety and recoverability, and supports improvisation rather than scripted protocols. Our system complements

Figure 2: The architecture of the proposed WoZ platform.

rather than duplicates these prior systems, filling a gap for fast, safe, operator-friendly WoZ tools in educational CRI/HRI contexts.

Efficient WoZ platforms are also motivated by the need to reduce costs and logistical challenges when deploying real robots in HRIs [6, 20]. Recent developments highlight the growing interest in adaptable interfaces [2] and authoring tools that could support the setup of contextualized user studies in an easy and efficient manner [12]. While this prior work focuses on structured WoZ interfaces suited for predefined HRI experiments, we aim to provide a tool that supports dynamic adaptation to unpredictable situations.

The originality of our contribution lies in shifting from a solution designed to assist researchers and designers in running structured experiments, to one that offers **flexibility and supports improvisation**. This allows adaptation to the unpredictability of real users’ behavior while enabling researchers to gain insights to guide the design of more natural interactions. The proposed WoZ finds direct application in the growing field of CRI, but can also be easily deployed in unstructured HRI contexts.

2 Objective and Proposed Solution

The main objective of our work is to provide the HRI community with a general-purpose, user-friendly, and adaptive WoZ platform that can handle improvisation. Furthermore, we advocate that both robots designed to interact with people and the tools used to develop these interactions should be human-centered, accounting for users’ needs from early stage of development. To this end, we adopt a user-centered iterative design approach in the development of our WoZ platform. Via a number of make-and-look iterations we grasped a better understanding of user needs and extracted user requirements of a group of researchers in human-computer interactions, with no specific technical background in robotics, representing the initial targets of the dashboard. In our design and implementation, we considered the specific requirements of a tool meant to support researchers during the inherently unstructured process of usage research. To this end, we accounted for improvisation that is inevitably required when assisting users interacting with robots in real-world work context.

Figure 2 illustrates the overall structure of our system. At the core of the architecture is a *Graphical User Interface (GUI)* that enables operators to easily customize the robot’s dashboard by adding buttons, sliders, joysticks, and visualization tools. Buttons are used to conveniently send commands to the *Robot* module, whereas sliders are used to modulate their intensity. Visualization tools, on the other hand, are used to receive messages from the *Robot* and provide the operator with feedback about the interaction.

Two kinds of commands are sent to the robot by the operator through the GUI. The first type consists of *General-purpose Commands*, which include standard robot commands (e.g., base’s wheels velocity, or arm’s joint positions). The latter are *Customized Commands* that operators can add to the dashboard to personalize their interaction experience according to the specific HRI task and robotic platform. Examples include controlling lighting patterns and modulating speaker sounds. Such Customized Commands pass through an *Adapter* module, which acts as a parser to make them compatible with the robot’s lower-level firmware. The Adapter is, in fact, the key component that makes our system versatile and deployable across robotic platforms. Each robot is given a dedicated Adapter module, which connects higher level commands (such as “move the arm”) to the robot’s control layer (e.g., its whole-body motion controller). The Adapter has proven particularly useful during the iterative design process, enabling us to adapt the dashboard to different users’ needs. Furthermore, it allowed us to easily construct various experimental setups, as demonstrated in Sec. 4.

Finally, the Robot sends *Feedback* signals to the GUI, informing the operator about the current state of the interaction. Common Feedback signals include data from the robot’s onboard sensors (e.g., raw camera stream) or other task-specific perception information, such as user-robot mutual gaze enabled by dedicated systems [3].

3 Software Architecture

This section explains implementation details realizing the proposed framework conceptually introduced in Fig. 2. The code implementing our WoZ solution is available at the following link: <https://github.com/idsia-robotics/wizard-for-kids>.

3.1 GUI Modules

The GUI consists of a web interface composed of two modules:

- **dashboard_gui**: The GUI is implemented as a web application using Next.js [19] and React [11]. It provides an intuitive interface that dynamically adapts, based on the selected robot’s capabilities. It features modular control panels for different robot functions (movement, manipulation, LEDs, sound), real-time camera feeds, and experiment management tools. The interface supports both mouse/keyboard and touch inputs, making it suitable for tablets and laptops. Examples of dashboards instantiated for the RoboMaster EP and TIAGo robot are shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 3, respectively.
- **dashboard_bridge**: A custom Node.js/Express server [9] that provides RESTful API endpoints for administrative functions such as starting/stopping ROS2 bag recording and managing robot configurations. This complements the direct ROS2 communication (handled by the `rosbridge_server`, introduced below), providing essential infrastructure services for experiment management and system configuration.

3.2 Core ROS2 Nodes

The GUI modules are complemented by two main ROS2 nodes:

- **rosbridge_server** provides the primary communication bridge between the web-based dashboard and the ROS2 ecosystem. It establishes a WebSocket connection enabling real-time bidirectional communication, by converting JSON

messages from the web interface into native ROS2 messages, and vice versa. This node handles data streams such as camera feeds, sensor readings, and motion commands¹.

- **dashboard_adapter** is a robot-specific adapter node that translates high-level semantic commands from the dashboard into robot-specific low-level control signals.

Each supported robot (e.g., RoboMaster EP, TIAGo) has a dedicated adapter that interprets standardized dashboard commands and executes appropriate behaviors via the robot’s native ROS2 interfaces. Measurements indicate low command latency: 0.1–2.1 ms (median 0.5 ms) running locally on the robot, and median 6.2 ms over Wi-Fi across four classroom deployments (95th percentile 17.6 ms), with rare outliers up to 104 ms. Furthermore, safety and recoverability measures include configurable robot velocity limits, an emergency stop button, and automatic stopping in case of connection loss.

3.3 Customized Topic Messages

Beyond the standardized topics provided by ROS2 and by the robot frameworks, our system defines a set of Customized Commands implemented as ROS2 topics and actions, properly designed for experiment control and logging:

- `/dashboard/movement`: high-level navigation commands (e.g., “go to user1”, “return to origin”).
- `/dashboard/arm`: robotic arm behaviors commands (e.g., “wave”, “open_box”, “shake_hands”).
- `/dashboard/gripper`: gripper operations with configurable force parameters (e.g., {action: “open, force: 0.5”}).
- `/dashboard/sound`: commands for pre-defined sound effects (e.g., “beep”, “happy_chime”, “encourage”).
- `/dashboard/leds`: LED patterns and color control for visual feedback (e.g., “rainbow”, “flash”, “pulse”).
- `/experiment/event`: to record structured experiment events in JSONL format, enabling comprehensive analysis of HRI sessions with precise timestamps and contextual metadata.

The actions associated with these topics enable full customization, as detailed in Section 4.1.

4 Usage Notes and Demonstrations

4.1 Easy customization

Our WoZ platform is designed for straightforward adaptation to new robotic platforms and experimental scenarios through two primary customization mechanisms.

The first is related to the robot platform: support for a new robot requires creating a dedicated `dashboard_adapter` that translates the custom dashboard commands into robot-specific actions. The Adapter subscribes to the customized command topics described in Sec. 3.3 and converts JSON-encoded messages into appropriate robot control calls. Leveraging existing ROS2 packages and action servers, the adapter can easily integrate with existing robot control frameworks. For instance, our TIAGo Adapter interprets custom movement commands like `PlayMotion2` [13] actions, enabling seamless integration with the robot’s motion planning system².

¹`rosbridge_suite`: https://github.com/RobotWebTools/rosbridge_suite

²An implementation of TIAGo adapter is available at: <https://github.com/idsia-robotics/wizard-for-kids-tiago>.

Figure 3: HRI experiments realized with our WoZ system.

The second customization mechanism is related to the dashboard configuration. The web interface dynamically adapts based on robot configuration files that specify available capabilities, semantic actions, and topic mappings. Users can easily customize the interface through the built-in configuration wizard, which allows them to add or remove control buttons (each representing a semantic action such as “wave”, “offer_object”), specify robot-specific parameters, and configure topic mappings directly within the web interface. This approach enables rapid prototyping of interaction scenarios without requiring code modifications, allowing users to focus on HRI design rather than technical implementation details.

On the repository we provide a video demonstrating the functional steps to adapt our WoZ system to a new robot.

4.2 Real-world robot experiments

We tested our system in two experimental settings. In the first one, we used the RoboMaster EP robot, manufactured by DJI Technology. This is a compact mobile platform (320 mm × 240 mm × 270 mm, 3.3 kg) equipped with omnidirectional wheels, LED lights, a loud-speaker, and a 2-axis arm with a gripper holding an automatically opening box. The robot enables non-verbal interaction by rotating, offering or accepting objects, expressing states via LEDs, and emitting sounds. It includes a Wi-Fi module for remote control and uses onboard sensors and motor encoders to localize itself without external infrastructure. These features facilitate flexible deployment outside the lab. Specifically, we deployed the robot in school settings and used the proposed WoZ interface to let it interact with children and play the role of a regulator or peer during the execution of a collaborative task. In this case the dashboard was equipped with buttons to let the robot emit different sounds and lights, and perform motion with the arm and the mobile base (see Fig. 1). Our system allowed easy iterative design of the experiments, listening to the needs of users (children) and operators. Furthermore, it also

allowed to easily control the robot in the complex schools settings, improvising robot behaviors to cope with the unpredictability of the children’s behaviors and handle large groups of kids.

In the second scenario, we employed a full-size PAL Robotics TIAGo robot (see Fig. 3), equipped with a differential drive base, a prismatic joint for torso movement, a 7-axis manipulator, and a head capable of panning $\pm 75^\circ$ and tilting from -60° to 45° relative to the horizontal plane. To enhance environmental perception, our robot is outfitted with a Microsoft Azure Kinect RGB-D camera mounted on the head, offering a 65° horizontal field of view and 15 Hz frame rate. Our TIAGo is also equipped with a tray at the end-effector, enabling it to offer treats to passersby. Indeed, we deployed TIAGo for HRI scenarios where it interacts with people sharing the same environment and offers them objects. In such experiments, an operator remotely controls the robot’s base to approach people, modulating its velocity appropriately and triggering the robot’s arm to perform the offering motion. Simultaneously, the operator monitors the interaction state by viewing the video stream captured by the robot’s onboard camera, which is promptly displayed in the WoZ interface, see Fig. 3. This scenario was aimed at validating the effectiveness of our WoZ system in listening to the needs of HRI researchers to quickly prototype interaction experiments.

The adaptation of the WoZ interface from one scenario to the other and the customization across tasks and robotic platforms was easy and straightforward, thanks to the steps explained in Sec. 3. The code repository also shows the videos of the experiments deploying our interface, showing its ease of use and versatility.

5 Conclusion

We have presented an interface to support improvisation, essential for the user-centered design of innovative HRI. In particular, we listened to and addressed the needs of researchers, with and without specific background in robotics, when running usage research activities geared at getting a better understanding of real users’ needs. The interface was tested in a real classroom and proved adaptable and robust enough to engage children and collect user data to inform the next steps of design. It also proved flexible enough to work within a different scenario and with another type of robot. These findings are encouraging enough to motivate us to pursue this line of investigation, even if we will need to test the interface in more scenarios and with different researchers and designers, to further assess usability with non-expert operators in future studies. Ease of use, intuitiveness, adaptability and customizability are important features for such an interface. Thus, it can be used to foster the involvement of multidisciplinary teams bringing different expertise essential in the study of human-robot interaction to complement technical skills and facilitate contextualized user studies.

We believe improvisation should be core when designing for users in unpredictable yet real work contexts and therefore this interface is a meaningful contribution to the robotics community at large and specifically to HRI researchers.

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